

nemo like kinase (NLK) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

Nemo-Like Kinase (NLK) is a serine/threonine protein kinase , Nemo (NMO) being the Drosophila ortholog of the mammalian NLK gene. Its activation mechanism and downstream targets are still not well characterized. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 NLK related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for NLK-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) and Sobol indices, WNT3A

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr NLK comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order NLK related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination,

then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. nemo like kinase (NLK)

The *Drosophila* eye consists of a reiterative hexagonal array of photoreceptor cell clusters, the ommatidia. During normal morphogenesis, the clusters in the dorsal or ventral halves of the disc rotate 90° in opposite directions, forming mirror images across a dorsoventral equator. In the mutant *nemo* (NMO), there is an initial turning of approximately 45° , but further rotation is blocked. Choi and Benzer [4] indicate that the NMO acts upon each cluster as a whole; normal *nmo* function in one or more photoreceptor cells appears to be sufficient to induce full rotation. The NMO gene sequence is required to initiate the second step of rotation, via an encoded serine/threonine protein kinase homolog. They show that in another mutant, *roulette*, excessive rotation through varying angles occurs in many ommatidia, which is suppressed by NMO, thus indicating that NMO acts upstream in a rotation-regulating pathway.

Extracellular-signal regulated kinases/microtubule-associated protein kinases (ERK/MAPKs) and cyclin-directed kinases (CDKs) are key regulators of many aspects of cell growth and division, as well as apoptosis. Brott et al. [5] cloned NLK, where the NLK amino acid sequence is 54.5% similar and 41.7% identical to murine ERK2, and 49.6% similar and 38.4% identical to human CDC2. A feature that distinguishes NLK from ERK/MAPKs, CDKs, and also NMO, is its extended amino-terminal domain, that is very rich in glutamine, alanine, proline, and histidine. Mutation of the ATP-binding Lys-155 to methionine abolishes its ability to autophosphorylate, as does mutation of a putative activating threonine in kinase domain VIII, to valine, aspartic, or glutamic acid. NLK and NMO may be the first members of a family of kinases with homology to both ERK/MAPKs and CDKs. Mitogen-activated protein (MAP) kinases are a family of serine/threonine kinases that transduce extracellular cues into a variety of intracellular responses ranging from lineage specification to cell division and adaptation. Coulombe and Meloche [6] classify MAP kinases into conventional or atypical enzymes, based on their ability to get phosphorylated and activated by the MAP kinase kinase (MAPKK)/MEK family. Conventional MAP kinases comprise ERK1/ERK2, p38s, JNKs, and ERK5, which are all substrates of MAPKKs, while atypical MAP kinases include ERK3/ERK4, NLK and ERK7. Much less is known about the regulation, substrate specificity and physiological functions of atypical MAP kinases.

Considering the structure of NLK, its C-terminal extension is conserved from worm to human (45% identity between LIT-1 and human NLK) and may contribute to the interaction of the kinase with specific substrates or targets as shown by Ishitani et al. [7]. The WNT signalling pathway regulates many developmental processes through

a complex of β -catenin and the T-cell factor/ lymphoid enhancer factor (TCF/LEF) family. WNT stabilizes cytosolic β -catenin, which then binds to TCF and activates gene transcription. In *Caenorhabditis elegans*, the proteins MOM4 and LIT1 regulate WNT signalling to polarize responding cells during embryogenesis as shown by Meneghini et al. [8]. MOM4 and LIT1 are homologous to TAK1 (a kinase activated by transforming growth factor- β) mitogenactivated protein-kinase-kinase kinase (MAP3K) and MAPK-related NLK, respectively, in mammalian cells. Ishitani et al. [7] hypothesize the possibility that TAK1 and NLK are also involved in WNT signalling in mammalian cells and show that TAK1 activation stimulates NLK activity and down-regulates transcriptional activation mediated by β -catenin and TCF. They demonstrate that injection of NLK suppresses the induction of axis duplication by microinjected β -catenin in *Xenopus* embryos. NLK phosphorylates TCF/LEF factors and inhibits the interaction of the β -catenin-TCF complex with DNA. Thus, the TAK1-NLK-MAPK-like pathway negatively regulates the WNT signalling pathway. Yamada et al. [9] and Yamada et al. [10], also show similar results of NLK interaction with TCF/LEF family members.

More specifically, *c-myb* proto-oncogene (*c-MYB*) regulates both the proliferation and apoptosis of hematopoietic cells by inducing the transcription of a group of target genes. Kanei-Ishii et al. [11] report that *c-MYB* protein is phosphorylated and degraded by WNT1 signal via the pathway involving TGF- β -activated kinase (TAK1), homeodomain-interacting protein kinase 2 (HIPK2), and NLK. They show that WNT1 signal causes the nuclear entry of TAK1, which then activates HIPK2 and NLK. Further, NLK binds directly to *c-MYB* together with HIPK2, which results in the phosphorylation of *c-MYB* at multiple sites, followed by its ubiquitination and proteasome-dependent degradation. Furthermore, overexpression of NLK in M1 cells abrogated the ability of *c-MYB* to maintain the undifferentiated state of these cells. Finally, Ishitani et al. [12] show that phosphorylation of TCF4 by NLK inhibited DNA binding by the β -catenin-TCF4 complex. These results suggested that NLK phosphorylation on these sites contributed to the down-regulation of LEF1/TCF transcriptional activity.

Ishitani and Ishitani [13] summarize the current understanding of the function and regulation of NLK and discuss the aspects of NLK regulation that remain to be resolved. In this research work, I present 3rd order combinations of NLK with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [14]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [14].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The

model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1].

For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 NLK-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [15]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [16] and martinez implementation in Martinez [17] and Baudin et al. [18]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested NLK-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving NLK were obtained from a full set of ${}^7C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of WNT-NLK-X combinations

Kanei-Ishii et al. [11] report that c-MYB protein is phosphorylated and degraded by WNT1 signal via the pathway involving TGF- β -activated kinase (TAK1), homeodomain-interacting protein kinase 2 (HIPK2), and NLK. They show that WNT1 signal causes the nuclear entry of TAK1, which then activates HIPK2 and NLK. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the WNT family along with NLK, to be prominent at 3rd order level - LRP5-NLK-WNT4, FOSL1-NLK-WNT4, CXXC4-NLK-WNT4, CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT5A, NLK-PORCN-WNT2B, NLK-PORCN-WNT2, LRP5-NLK-WNT2B, NLK-SFRP1-WNT5A, NLK-SFRP1-WNT2, NLK-SFRP1-WNT3, DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4, FRZB-NLK-WNT4, CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT2B, FZD1-NLK-WNT5A, CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT2B, LRP5-NLK-WNT5A, NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A, FZD5-NLK-WNT4, FGF4-NLK-WNT2B, CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT4, NLK-WIF1-WNT2, FRAT1-NLK-WNT4, NLK-WIF1-WNT2B, FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A,

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD1-NLK-SEN2	66	7254	6519	12561	16204	CSNK1G1-NLK-SEN2	74	35675	3308	48520	19328
LRP5-NLK-SEN2	99	17426	20510	156	54321	NLK-SFRP1-TCF7	125	43152	40831	35451	28596
LRP5-NLK-WNT4	173	5427	19931	576	56700	CSNK1D-FGF4-NLK	182	13641	35785	54873	12126
FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	308	14795	5137	12639	16597	CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT4	321	20710	3312	50831	31403
NLK-PORCN-PPP2CA	339	30605	43435	41734	4166	NLK-PORCN-SFRP4	368	53128	52278	37793	4619
FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	378	3397	2566	2260	40025	NLK-WIF1-WNT2	431	13840	49796	35119	6813
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	491	167	4767	2069	15953	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	534	1131	4271	13789	39755
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	591	19400	24702	2318	5774	CCND1-FGF4-NLK	650	37617	39188	40111	26729
BTRC-GSK3A-NLK	685	15173	52709	30778	8565	NLK-PORCN-SEN2	751	51440	56864	21216	6122
NLK-FBXW4-SLC9A3R1	760	5112	22367	45665	21602	FZD1-NLK-FBXW4	834	6168	26326	20481	40535
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT5A	840	10869	21909	56571	16909	LRP5-NLK-FBXW4	847	9156	37860	589	53712
CTNNBIP1-NLK-SFRP1	852	523	6419	55912	26165	NLK-WIF1-WNT2B	877	15574	29869	50706	14922
FZD1-NLK-SFRP1	923	208	3403	10308	46968	NLK-SFRP1-SFRP4	967	54433	34929	9753	40373
NLK-TLE1-TLE2	993	36487	34168	46840	34475	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	1005	19771	7884	9479	10249
NLK-PORCN-WNT2B	1006	26349	37659	35498	4512	FBXW2-FGF4-NLK	1060	19103	48572	41780	1397
LRP5-NLK-SFRP1	1066	2	18438	235	53114	NLK-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	1108	35858	56545	26507	3768
FZD1-NLK-TLE1	1147	12376	4310	27950	16973	NLK-PORCN-TCF7	1154	48490	41769	34836	12221
FBXW11-FGF4-NLK	1172	27458	51060	40627	25175	CSNK1G1-NLK-TLE1	1270	15559	1608	53075	20188
DKK1-NLK-SEN2	1343	20532	9328	35918	23556	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	1425	3331	440	49507	31594
CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	1467	3249	13379	2815	22591	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	1512	2335	4160	3374	12963
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	1520	3860	3645	1038	15312	DKK1-FGF4-NLK	1530	30108	32527	40415	19377
NLK-PORCN-WNT2	1557	46116	57071	36752	14418	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	1570	6400	25113	13146	24103
DAAMI-FGF4-NLK	1615	51287	55713	52792	17270	NLK-PORCN-TLE2	1657	49377	56092	39434	12430
LRP5-NLK-WNT2B	1725	4903	8642	34617	54453	NLK-PORCN-WNT4	1742	49908	50644	30880	6042
AES-AXINI-NLK	1775	49282	47808	50035	53907	FZD1-NLK-WNT2B	1840	1616	1306	53698	22012
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	1846	2471	1853	521	54004	FZD7-NLK-WNT3A	1957	2219	4173	15212	30086
NLK-SFRP1-WNT5A	2032	55480	32725	47613	26430	FGF4-NLK-WNT4	2033	3044	4724	33423	28154
NLK-SFRP1-WNT2	2043	53015	46284	12054	33556	DVL2-JUN-NLK	2045	6588	32911	20097	18489
NLK-SFRP1-WNT3	2049	43102	31587	4584	28785	FZD8-NLK-WNT2B	2126	25291	1834	45776	56354
DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	2128	13920	3978	2846	15403	CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	2202	5290	1484	56489	12898
CTNNB1-NLK-TLE1	2322	31661	2654	17390	15058	FZD8-NLK-SFRP1	2340	2987	4568	21448	52792
CTBP1-FGF4-NLK	2373	24017	40861	28523	25856	NLK-PORCN-TCF7L1	2400	38016	56402	27460	3015
CSNK1G1-NLK-TCF7L1	2409	13940	8988	50696	40050	DVL1-FGF4-NLK	2505	55303	42133	41000	49492
FRZB-NLK-WNT4	2520	1556	5592	7221	22356	FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	2530	6281	12625	8358	38149
DVL2-FGF4-NLK	2539	9068	35433	35003	33783	FZD5-FGF4-NLK	2548	25184	37573	26783	23902
AES-EP300-NLK	2549	52374	48380	27425	55437	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT4	2750	2726	9906	45186	25621
BCL9-FGF4-NLK	2765	16506	49200	35441	40551	CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	2780	22054	41988	28791	40205
FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK	2897	3423	17764	15937	45601	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	3007	15229	33503	42544	8088
CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT2B	3057	20612	364	49392	38971	FZD1-NLK-PPP2R1A	3063	6647	16715	10003	26509
GSK3B-NLK-TLE1	3123	28197	2579	41126	15983	LRP5-NLK-SFRP4	3199	217	20954	446	56950
FZD1-NLK-WNT5A	3220	14961	17555	36449	16975	CTNNBIP1-NLK-FBXW4	3223	10049	26324	48138	19000
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT2B	3262	12256	1539	46850	31899	CSNK1A1-NLK-TLE1	3280	2505	5178	30696	38811
LRP5-NLK-WNT5A	3296	15243	30086	6594	47805	CTNNBIP1-NLK-RHOU	3322	501	7291	43407	48933
NLK-PORCN-TLE1	3414	46190	49745	10954	11706	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	3436	6471	26909	5680	17650
FBXW2-JUN-NLK	3505	12581	49210	43684	51663	CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT4	3546	4416	6989	50022	30148
FZD5-NLK-SEN2	3647	23886	4036	3124	1472	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT3A	3672	3466	7618	26301	5357
LRP5-NLK-PPP2R1A	3749	6866	25722	95	55900	CSNK1G1-NLK-PPP2R1A	3754	21618	10600	22928	48421
NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A	3762	18958	12589	35118	5530	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	3843	4771	10375	1945	20127
FZD5-NLK-WNT4	3897	19032	2692	1966	40749	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	3902	24187	13268	22163	37611
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	3929	35214	17635	44956	38660	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	3932	2627	16679	25816	15722
NLK-SFRP1-TLE2	3952	54493	39629	26154	50386	DKK1-GSK3A-NLK	3968	22383	24849	47754	29762
FGF4-NLK-WNT2B	3978	2527	804	55492	27607	FOSL1-NLK-SFRP4	3991	8084	2347	4123	43458
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	4074	18571	5441	22722	18400	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	4096	7150	14882	4380	42041
CTNNBIP1-NLK-PPP2R1A	4168	17696	21970	43414	47292	NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	4229	27445	40800	13988	7354
AXINI-FZD2-NLK	4347	26298	10959	26949	9217	NLK-WIF1-WNT4	4406	21046	38575	49983	13952
NLK-SFRP1-FBXW4	4416	23473	46584	11984	39379	GSK3A-JUN-NLK	4439	45904	37849	40408	18195
AXINI-FOXN1-NLK	4448	7290	24395	14630	18096	FZD1-NLK-SFRP4	4509	3076	5015	18937	38268
CXXC4-NLK-RHOU	4522	5467	5985	8707	24421	DVL1-FOXN1-NLK	4529	51079	27843	11249	56056
FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1	4642	24230	11921	14016	23504	CCND3-FGF4-NLK	4644	49910	36053	48791	53135
DAAMI-FRAT1-NLK	4668	52014	25172	20469	49769	NLK-WIF1-WNT3A	4697	36349	45660	34357	1641
CTNNB1-NLK-WIF1	4707	9899	6192	11981	1923	FOSL1-NLK-TCF7L1	4743	4810	5264	1752	28982
CSNK1D-NLK-SEN2	4773	12377	9957	43796	3597	CSNK1A1-NLK-WIF1	4795	14710	6213	20851	31609
FRAT1-NLK-TCF7	4821	5072	6111	23919	29394	CCND1-NLK-WNT2B	4835	38149	1102	53863	38938

Table 1: Rankings of NLK-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B, FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A, NLK-PORCN-WNT4, FZD1-NLK-WNT2B, FZD7-NLK-WNT3A, FGF4-NLK-WNT4, FZD8-NLK-WNT2B, CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B, CSNK1D-NLK-WNT4, CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT4, CSNK1D-NLK-WNT3A, CXXC4-

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD1-NLK-SENP2	4216	33313	50995	20046	16713	CSNK1G1-NLK-SENP2	34480	34469	25805	4202	8014
LRP5-NLK-SENP2	28404	31921	48677	23545	26406	NLK-SFRP1-TCF7	8841	43619	30305	17506	12968
LRP5-NLK-WNT4	34513	16387	35220	5468	37281	CSNK1D-FGF4-NLK	5343	27561	8638	8497	51980
FRAT1-NLK-SENP2	47712	35472	55874	27952	35046	CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT4	37117	32429	26444	1650	27288
NLK-PORCN-PPP2CA	6640	37879	19229	30844	45007	NLK-PORCN-SFRP4	26548	54453	3595	31340	34837
FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	46914	7268	50547	1274	44200	NLK-WIF1-WNT2	40307	10226	11647	34273	29809
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	22955	3089	37410	121	47163	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	32436	4345	56234	697	36071
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	36361	6924	5576	32715	39457	CCND1-FGF4-NLK	23150	32232	22665	42559	12440
BTRC-GSK3A-NLK	8965	2718	45185	45189	49869	NLK-PORCN-SENP2	25839	52725	11882	9881	37272
NLK-FBXW4-SLC9A3R1	56671	1861	38594	29352	5573	FZD1-NLK-FBXW4	20283	8207	32619	27566	30042
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT5A	43965	11033	40662	17048	49376	LRP5-NLK-FBXW4	48704	10826	12482	34528	35402
CTNNBIP1-NLK-SFRP1	33298	2286	54426	26390	24484	NLK-WIF1-WNT2B	20533	18090	8143	25594	25892
FZD1-NLK-SFRP1	24451	9305	49446	19196	22902	NLK-SFRP1-SFRP4	25125	53640	1360	15834	31791
NLK-TLE1-TLE2	54439	46207	309	27068	8231	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	51049	30143	52377	44271	42168
NLK-PORCN-WNT2B	30300	3466	8133	31316	44880	FBXW2-FGF4-NLK	1671	979	163	29649	18596
LRP5-NLK-SFRP1	38815	3342	52455	23786	33500	NLK-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	39803	20122	9428	9998	42527
FZD1-NLK-TLE1	32959	8717	41662	33327	32893	NLK-PORCN-TCF7	14350	41604	26400	15610	37827
FBXW11-FGF4-NLK	2114	16567	7954	26999	37518	CSNK1G1-NLK-TLE1	51469	19124	38302	32990	19686
DKK1-NLK-SENP2	2831	28851	33433	831	12425	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	20492	705	35136	30860	53018
CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	21331	11904	46279	1885	30976	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	51755	5242	44005	49978	52983
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	49331	4153	49861	27131	33193	DKK1-FGF4-NLK	3129	15113	40241	34444	48762
NLK-PORCN-WNT2	44692	38504	8829	1995	53685	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	50800	21515	31927	26376	27004
DAAMI-FGF4-NLK	1482	50392	22580	43523	38010	NLK-PORCN-TLE2	41691	54802	745	25237	46608
LRP5-NLK-WNT2B	28396	1960	19941	23600	55297	NLK-PORCN-WNT4	33383	45823	7542	34942	49961
AES-AXIN1-NLK	32068	45433	3161	29821	53403	FZD1-NLK-WNT2B	28935	4414	27054	36546	52981
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	34233	941	55096	25592	35663	FZD7-NLK-WNT3A	23365	3018	51679	44843	19133
NLK-SFRP1-WNT5A	22263	52123	16817	33554	46452	FGF4-NLK-WNT4	4835	2733	36815	3654	11745
NLK-SFRP1-WNT2	33812	54135	6702	29330	45088	DVL2-JUN-NLK	17072	6052	41009	20313	44474
NLK-SFRP1-WNT3	51886	35916	3457	20064	40670	FZD8-NLK-WNT2B	50248	4499	42098	23442	25585
DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	5010	8900	42377	1999	3181	CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	28869	300	28004	21112	54426
CTNNB1-NLK-TLE1	55950	22712	28147	35986	13653	FZD8-NLK-SFRP1	54470	72	56582	18335	33221
CTBP1-FGF4-NLK	3746	33288	10452	55841	49146	NLK-PORCN-TCF7L1	31569	44836	10175	2151	43393
CSNK1G1-NLK-TCF7L1	38665	6811	44713	7792	48500	DVL1-FGF4-NLK	2306	54597	5405	53929	25428
FRZB-NLK-WNT4	6001	9443	53325	4130	50442	FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	26675	24348	52446	8545	15016
DVL2-FGF4-NLK	2327	15184	45235	14257	45259	FZD5-FGF4-NLK	2239	33059	12033	52334	51042
AES-EP300-NLK	38886	52106	1233	23736	42435	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT4	1538	21775	47534	6449	28873
BCL9-FGF4-NLK	6693	29487	24244	44096	45853	CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	1507	4569	5986	44776	54536
FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK	345	17553	4941	12084	9525	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	17474	18226	16777	16181	28351
CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT2B	53434	5922	42619	33337	50690	FZD1-NLK-PPP2R1A	20834	8886	52092	12766	24248
GSK3B-NLK-TLE1	45736	20255	50690	4684	15971	LRP5-NLK-SFRP4	42299	6001	52599	18512	34951
FZD1-NLK-WNT5A	28100	15641	23012	14962	49066	CTNNBIP1-NLK-FBXW4	44996	19802	33841	25211	38562
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT2B	23541	1910	34449	30631	55521	CSNK1A1-NLK-TLE1	16274	1109	56566	37347	24936
LRP5-NLK-WNT5A	33250	14809	24503	18293	46276	CTNNBIP1-NLK-RHOU	20208	392	56468	42238	24576
NLK-PORCN-TLE1	37435	39499	5549	31543	47543	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	25837	3880	29684	25017	18802
FBXW2-JUN-NLK	29577	33489	631	40952	3561	CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT4	27403	2923	45312	850	52767
FZD5-NLK-SENP2	9566	34294	49065	9629	25330	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT3A	12770	9632	43802	42949	37641
LRP5-NLK-PPP2R1A	22739	10079	12169	17484	38120	CSNK1G1-NLK-PPP2R1A	35195	9424	21823	20710	43474
NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A	26514	5505	28475	52773	4096	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	38206	4994	56442	3145	46853
FZD5-NLK-WNT4	18569	6862	45684	649	46844	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	1488	36811	54049	43805	46079
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	26521	15175	17461	50164	8676	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	46697	2350	52931	39870	42513
NLK-SFRP1-TLE2	44300	56949	757	34474	28195	DKK1-GSK3A-NLK	28	36037	55819	40750	50385
FGF4-NLK-WNT2B	13475	808	24001	38421	32951	FOSL1-NLK-SFRP4	56020	1030	45227	15474	45886
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	52049	4579	56808	43475	33170	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	47257	5675	39028	27369	25057
CTNNBIP1-NLK-PPP2R1A	27842	23336	43647	19091	40032	NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	7759	3583	13307	7257	24124
AXIN1-FZD2-NLK	17740	18892	23208	35290	20140	NLK-WIF1-WNT4	27894	29051	3153	6969	7790
NLK-SFRP1-FBXW4	21614	5912	9190	38148	35118	GSK3A-JUN-NLK	12859	53370	40655	43079	36718
AXIN1-FOXN1-NLK	9541	19853	27767	42655	28011	FZD1-NLK-SFRP4	28087	13170	30488	13854	38484
CXXC4-NLK-RHOU	43136	740	51616	39219	36924	DVL1-FOXN1-NLK	3090	52566	51110	49483	15813
FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1	6486	13405	43996	6473	42827	CCND3-FGF4-NLK	277	51087	6136	52041	3116
DAAMI-FRAT1-NLK	48108	52925	26046	49813	10162	NLK-WIF1-WNT3A	15025	31663	634	53620	7624
CTNNB1-NLK-WIF1	36869	4645	37317	37303	40718	FOSL1-NLK-TCF7L1	10193	14999	53644	2916	50012
CSNK1D-NLK-SENP2	2789	23569	46292	12953	16278	CSNK1A1-NLK-WIF1	11282	8274	56968	38447	50254
FRAT1-NLK-TCF7	46859	4510	41103	2141	38466	CCND1-NLK-WNT2B	9124	21736	38415	27714	2883

Table 2: Rankings of NLK-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

NLK-WNT5A, NLK-PYGO1-WNT2, NLK-WIF1-WNT4, NLK-WIF1-WNT3A and CCND1-NLK-WNT2B. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD1-NLK-SENP2	32881	56429	40609	50897	13532	CSNK1G1-NLK-SENP2	14817	11675	2225	15674	28868
LRP5-NLK-SENP2	54975	52944	33505	52497	5925	NLK-SFRP1-TCF7	50625	2336	45351	47084	6147
LRP5-NLK-WNT4	48309	18357	56155	51944	12470	CSNK1D-FGF4-NLK	11305	41185	24087	8932	35872
FRAT1-NLK-SENP2	30840	31831	43075	52500	657	CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT4	7646	8437	104	10192	43063
NLK-PORCN-PPP2CA	2376	11307	5767	13480	29665	NLK-PORCN-SFRP4	1207	52071	4041	14592	51831
FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	11701	13725	13502	3308	41595	NLK-WIF1-WNT2	8017	43046	20756	8948	54881
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	53246	51233	55370	49749	15337	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	35248	26254	44997	50913	4522
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	5974	6674	24560	10110	44194	CCND1-FGF4-NLK	13679	54223	12866	4826	40572
BTRC-GSK3A-NLK	3999	6285	26940	4495	55882	NLK-PORCN-SENP2	700	5829	4828	22993	34644
NLK-FBXW4-SLC9A3R1	6672	944	17483	6450	37821	FZD1-NLK-FBXW4	27044	14937	20064	3441	47974
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT5A	20035	789	8556	6531	46843	LRP5-NLK-FBXW4	25639	29849	2127	7364	49495
CTNNBIP1-NLK-SFRP1	15612	51263	6516	3246	44948	NLK-WIF1-WNT2B	49149	14168	36378	48222	2298
FZD1-NLK-SFRP1	23952	17617	12380	20314	50925	NLK-SFRP1-SFRP4	37781	11607	40591	39624	11082
NLK-TLE1-TLE2	80	10397	21544	11303	37932	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	21933	31321	12151	6237	52766
NLK-PORCN-WNT2B	53778	43223	50000	50320	693	FBXW2-FGF4-NLK	18618	24502	22118	9703	46811
LRP5-NLK-SFRP1	5963	19740	2919	3516	29709	NLK-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	12654	19526	884	5614	49323
FZD1-NLK-TLE1	30848	52091	33715	54030	26954	NLK-PORCN-TCF7	1320	10309	1882	15974	55425
FBXW11-FGF4-NLK	23311	1900	14413	23518	20157	CSNK1G1-NLK-TLE1	21496	36188	1461	20150	44770
DKK1-NLK-SENP2	54752	2748	44492	37392	9042	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	42013	9877	52887	52662	11462
CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	9628	4363	7425	17260	48958	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	43309	33771	50006	38500	4467
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	17728	56469	8386	24896	33148	DKK1-FGF4-NLK	14178	14417	23539	2527	44810
NLK-PORCN-WNT2	3371	14108	7182	6820	56445	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	27208	27395	8069	9031	35043
DAAM1-FGF4-NLK	22842	41365	14456	9376	26084	NLK-PORCN-TLE2	56416	24825	38132	40938	7611
LRP5-NLK-WNT2B	5246	28793	23635	4377	51925	NLK-PORCN-WNT4	3277	2846	7185	12509	42889
AES-AXIN1-NLK	9498	18559	2097	26325	47302	FZD1-NLK-WNT2B	26886	12820	19770	537	36921
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	43758	21393	56612	37171	12178	FZD7-NLK-WNT3A	56722	52305	45867	39848	966
NLK-SFRP1-WNT5A	7723	23039	14415	17477	48341	FGF4-NLK-WNT4	41389	35281	52350	41017	19285
NLK-SFRP1-WNT2	43250	21759	31860	43677	3362	DVL2-JUN-NLK	29029	47326	43928	46867	17282
NLK-SFRP1-WNT3	44829	656	45881	39104	19798	FZD8-NLK-WNT2B	14741	29006	21177	7164	20844
DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	16250	51618	16235	15399	35237	CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	17363	10111	1772	5324	38194
CTNNB1-NLK-TLE1	27872	32840	1645	25243	35386	FZD8-NLK-SFRP1	82	47110	21402	19634	41486
CTBP1-FGF4-NLK	15322	52729	476	18863	41931	NLK-PORCN-TCF7L1	55837	46734	55270	41203	1680
CSNK1G1-NLK-TCF7L1	44331	44573	53183	44188	4910	DVL1-FGF4-NLK	17900	49662	6898	605	38265
FRZB-NLK-WNT4	36879	4793	38330	40342	8139	FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	25915	28518	16997	20251	33293
DVL2-FGF4-NLK	28213	2105	18467	7591	54387	FZD5-FGF4-NLK	16664	48435	16179	20385	40900
AES-EP300-NLK	28608	36332	44162	32492	15003	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT4	41521	25413	31966	31421	31114
BCL9-FGF4-NLK	38883	33426	39880	33931	9949	CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	18745	698	6566	18659	49649
FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK	32212	50740	44453	46568	13089	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	39610	21989	44077	55924	5573
CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT2B	49065	6850	56800	44447	6716	FZD1-NLK-PPP2R1A	24761	3213	17679	9061	47517
GSK3B-NLK-TLE1	30246	18199	42550	36479	9782	LRP5-NLK-SFRP4	51151	37477	54256	53628	27949
FZD1-NLK-WNT5A	26056	2877	20780	17408	38034	CTNNBIP1-NLK-FBXW4	8586	21149	4834	2841	49037
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT2B	5208	6106	7353	13039	39823	CSNK1A1-NLK-TLE1	34554	35813	30941	38569	6273
LRP5-NLK-WNT5A	7424	17108	1077	11334	46700	CTNNBIP1-NLK-RHOU	1785	9526	2470	12825	45699
NLK-PORCN-TLE1	738	33306	18978	16241	49395	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	54866	7550	40448	43753	13270
FBXW2-JUN-NLK	48440	55202	39832	57113	40299	CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT4	39795	45149	54515	50600	16562
FZD5-NLK-SENP2	56148	1106	54384	44372	18787	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT3A	15647	31281	25207	25693	26652
LRP5-NLK-PPP2R1A	3984	29481	13824	21011	33733	CSNK1G1-NLK-PPP2R1A	44178	38444	50560	39549	2806
NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A	54945	28493	36640	50844	4694	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	20204	45005	6311	11503	39338
FZD5-NLK-WNT4	54895	46142	53067	48068	7256	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	29885	38529	45890	51667	3052
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	4589	40067	18292	17467	37330	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	12448	41748	17765	12599	37639
NLK-SFRP1-TLE2	6559	1417	10364	10258	51921	DKK1-GSK3A-NLK	5199	56282	12659	802	24641
FGF4-NLK-WNT2B	13983	13082	5260	6777	42385	FOSL1-NLK-SFRP4	22347	1314	4218	16632	43421
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	26333	25024	14059	4672	56498	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	28123	53372	22683	12683	35312
CTNNBIP1-NLK-PPP2R1A	9258	4462	1417	3718	45909	NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	7875	21489	20941	18370	48652
AXIN1-FZD2-NLK	5557	45525	14718	5992	29080	NLK-WIF1-WNT4	8622	27260	19165	3572	56997
NLK-SFRP1-FBXW4	6973	2397	15511	19687	29641	GSK3A-JUN-NLK	54928	43307	37092	34931	195
AXIN1-FOXN1-NLK	29905	47318	33516	42967	1593	FZD1-NLK-SFRP4	33166	39689	44749	36859	6194
CXXC4-NLK-RHOU	11487	36211	1937	21	26603	DVL1-FOXN1-NLK	51512	8920	38068	38206	19880
FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1	26303	8522	23444	3117	30365	CCND3-FGF4-NLK	9701	43197	2829	7621	54290
DAAM1-FRAT1-NLK	4271	40821	23704	20719	32697	NLK-WIF1-WNT3A	38872	26733	39808	47467	11370
CTNNB1-NLK-WIF1	27962	27173	4445	7873	33696	FOSL1-NLK-TCF7L1	46679	50596	53532	36721	4909
CSNK1D-NLK-SENP2	40143	16432	28881	34696	27936	CSNK1A1-NLK-WIF1	32459	19376	28696	36711	12615
FRAT1-NLK-TCF7	31025	10786	45374	32514	5601	CCND1-NLK-WNT2B	1466	147	2076	15099	47918

Table 3: Rankings of NLK-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of TCF-NLK-X combinations

Ishitani et al. [12] show that phosphorylation of TCF4 by NLK inhibited DNA binding by the β -catenin-TCF4 complex. These results suggested that NLK phosphorylation

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FZD1-NLK-SENP2	38601	38210	1256	1993	12948	CSNK1G1-NLK-SENP2	1023	28963	23752	12006	13662
LRP5-NLK-SENP2	20156	45164	15815	450	10120	NLK-SFRP1-TCF7	15763	45610	44238	53158	23900
LRP5-NLK-WNT4	11875	29409	39497	717	14614	CSNK1D-FGF4-NLK	33940	4625	12426	23698	5080
FRAT1-NLK-SENP2	23247	35162	2221	25952	18481	CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT4	9882	34667	14911	20141	31237
NLK-PORCN-PPP2CA	37331	14886	22559	45950	6790	NLK-PORCN-SFRP4	10994	18306	26888	51840	4032
FOSL1-NLK-WNT4	45098	10285	6164	24489	8061	NLK-WIF1-WNT2	8814	45087	57018	56594	46968
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	55944	14516	7372	46062	23888	FRAT1-NLK-WNT4	25990	49738	661	19315	9889
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	20852	11273	14078	12143	34383	CCND1-FGF4-NLK	36956	50100	12565	29461	2488
BTRC-GSK3A-NLK	8078	21590	4643	7767	37219	NLK-PORCN-SENP2	9588	21743	36008	30568	4545
NLK-FBXW4-SLC9A3R1	50323	56493	55382	51089	1283	FZD1-NLK-FBXW4	1849	57116	22582	23097	45034
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT5A	10769	10715	43199	6383	43941	LRP5-NLK-FBXW4	46245	52768	25791	7477	42323
CTNNBIP1-NLK-SFRP1	5440	42820	30699	52712	7141	NLK-WIF1-WNT2B	27488	14739	50681	54964	10671
FZD1-NLK-SFRP1	3786	56744	7272	4788	51185	NLK-SFRP1-SFRP4	8319	53182	26431	47936	19783
NLK-TLE1-TLE2	44450	40994	46592	10912	27253	FRAT1-NLK-WNT3A	39223	41587	3411	8849	50359
FZD1-NLK-SFRP1	23304	40640	40983	7483	30297	FBXW2-FGF4-NLK	29965	54954	45312	39042	4018
LRP5-NLK-SFRP1	54239	14961	26224	50308	5787	NLK-PORCN-SLC9A3R1	17046	52346	6586	54426	44843
FZD1-NLK-TLE1	34624	46823	6476	226	17244	NLK-PORCN-TCF7	1798	29061	14067	37353	4424
FBXW11-FGF4-NLK	42960	11281	32914	3677	8822	CSNK1G1-NLK-TLE1	5572	45737	24235	16306	30837
DKK1-NLK-SENP2	17487	9683	24838	40503	3603	FOSL1-NLK-WNT2B	14329	18478	43731	32209	46898
CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	13188	19135	45004	13965	42668	FOSL1-NLK-WNT3A	14627	8003	43826	49427	54343
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	39174	27767	26220	7903	4356	DKK1-FGF4-NLK	3100	53962	56105	50767	26310
NLK-PORCN-WNT2	20516	13167	13537	26978	5995	FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4	18761	55322	24209	45107	1970
DAAMI-FGF4-NLK	3535	11936	56459	37947	20858	NLK-PORCN-TLE2	54185	50313	41574	46224	37007
LRP5-NLK-WNT2B	12533	30603	27930	42546	28598	NLK-PORCN-WNT4	839	35865	37133	52537	3763
AES-AXIN1-NLK	28575	9759	7476	17704	9574	FZD1-NLK-WNT2B	3078	19116	35164	4311	41638
FOSL1-NLK-SFRP1	20605	4506	43594	44065	56286	FZD7-NLK-WNT3A	56916	32082	34420	55311	39594
NLK-SFRP1-WNT5A	1980	50539	36522	25586	2949	FGF4-NLK-WNT4	7085	8398	45782	12210	41629
NLK-SFRP1-WNT2	8863	53446	40389	48753	37911	DVL2-JUN-NLK	24365	41288	6993	49860	37247
NLK-SFRP1-WNT3	11209	36143	39139	50500	40204	FZD8-NLK-WNT2B	8180	25506	12029	17752	3665
DIXDC1-NLK-WNT4	1935	7729	30708	20858	4426	CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	7556	34332	12045	46119	55583
CTNNB1-NLK-TLE1	49657	4874	55497	18521	47934	FZD8-NLK-SFRP1	50563	21578	33954	7117	5766
CTBP1-FGF4-NLK	1106	18309	1506	9725	35430	NLK-PORCN-TCF7L1	39190	22916	48159	51082	21390
CSNK1G1-NLK-TCF7L1	25249	40044	11018	25277	24236	DVL1-FGF4-NLK	23402	6451	9264	15993	5706
FRZB-NLK-WNT4	20535	24126	28511	55751	12292	FRAT1-NLK-TLE2	6165	41726	15518	10280	22478
DVL2-FGF4-NLK	14667	19791	55123	53608	41359	FZD5-FGF4-NLK	68	9065	15857	9115	49660
AES-EP300-NLK	10828	53497	40369	49022	8923	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT4	55088	4562	19617	29935	54873
BCL9-FGF4-NLK	11767	50814	28974	2607	20092	CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	2855	14468	54057	56608	16142
FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK	48187	49175	16622	926	18742	FSHB-FZD2-NLK	40955	45035	3571	2400	7322
CSNK1G1-NLK-WNT2B	51130	36723	22493	41024	14440	FZD1-NLK-PPP2R1A	14161	20148	41005	22371	49081
GSK3B-NLK-TLE1	8204	16474	902	31073	38798	LRP5-NLK-SFRP4	9133	42676	44920	14150	23981
FZD1-NLK-WNT5A	5156	51064	50988	8427	47484	CTNNBIP1-NLK-FBXW4	28192	9202	39576	32506	47874
CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT2B	21928	14475	35204	4399	35883	CSNK1A1-NLK-TLE1	56242	25711	3977	25404	37414
LRP5-NLK-WNT5A	45036	52213	6262	10225	16127	CTNNBIP1-NLK-RHOU	28147	3381	3458	1969	48016
NLK-PORCN-TLE1	22044	56594	18300	44805	1801	DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4	22603	4145	2181	34664	55633
FBXW2-JUN-NLK	12342	305	49579	40611	11208	CTNNBIP1-NLK-WNT4	36958	26277	141	35655	22686
FZD5-NLK-SENP2	25984	24509	29600	43373	33546	CSNK1D-NLK-WNT3A	30261	5484	6297	36145	38245
LRP5-NLK-PPP2R1A	12943	44041	12550	26240	4030	CSNK1G1-NLK-PPP2R1A	20710	56117	30444	20124	29195
NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A	17677	56249	39251	46980	41057	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	6370	40057	51079	27610	27206
FZD5-NLK-WNT4	50572	52535	36426	48777	53517	EP300-GSK3A-NLK	29218	53879	34237	18183	8594
CCND1-FRAT1-NLK	10379	19677	54361	54552	23021	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	32823	7902	18426	32670	44201
NLK-SFRP1-TLE2	36833	32747	46317	40758	3998	DKK1-GSK3A-NLK	25274	3158	29299	39160	47089
FGF4-NLK-WNT2B	50224	56122	5603	8907	50245	FOSL1-NLK-SFRP4	36419	47157	5709	47580	23402
FRAT1-NLK-RHOU	4145	49061	13623	12994	32771	FRAT1-NLK-PPP2R1A	81	37116	49362	15818	45457
CTNNBIP1-NLK-PPP2R1A	14880	54925	8361	17662	47801	NLK-PYGO1-WNT2	20464	41550	50440	17275	1201
AXIN1-FZD2-NLK	21599	45257	23315	14802	5560	NLK-WIF1-WNT4	1987	42325	56959	36622	45848
NLK-SFRP1-FBXW4	45350	49944	55035	47305	2875	GSK3A-JUN-NLK	50339	32405	80	8041	28593
AXIN1-FOXN1-NLK	6320	39234	38453	37299	23011	FZD1-NLK-SFRP4	49398	56023	375	466	10392
CXXC4-NLK-RHOU	12582	34620	44443	19743	17071	DVL1-FOXN1-NLK	19607	37367	6301	20828	37423
FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1	3608	24939	48610	1803	26258	CCND3-FGF4-NLK	49332	1300	23452	53966	7825
DAAMI-FRAT1-NLK	31777	30000	56644	27373	6156	NLK-WIF1-WNT3A	9557	16952	33543	54081	7414
CTNNB1-NLK-WIF1	50485	2227	39887	31399	31013	FOSL1-NLK-TCF7L1	14353	25979	41399	42756	56811
CSNK1D-NLK-SENP2	54274	1758	35987	36243	51006	CSNK1A1-NLK-WIF1	30129	8991	3923	16574	38964
FRAT1-NLK-TCF7	28175	38761	5741	5244	11508	CCND1-NLK-WNT2B	54723	29128	46885	7628	47909

Table 4: Rankings of NLK-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

on these sites contributed to the down-regulation of LEF1/TCF transcriptional activity. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the TCF family along with NLK, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CSNK1G1-

NLK-TCF7L1, FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1, FRAT1-NLK-TCF7, NLK-SFRP1-TCF7, NLK-PORCN-TCF7, NLK-PORCN-TCF7L1, CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1 and FOSL1-NLK-TCF7L1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of FBXW-NLK-X combinations

Kanei-Ishii et al. [11] report that c-MYB protein is phosphorylated and degraded by WNT1 signal via the pathway involving TGF- β -activated kinase (TAK1), homeodomain-interacting protein kinase 2 (HIPK2), and NLK. They show that WNT1 signal causes the nuclear entry of TAK1, which then activates HIPK2 and NLK. Further, NLK binds directly to c-MYB together with HIPK2, which results in the phosphorylation of c-MYB at multiple sites, followed by its ubiquitination and proteasome-dependent degradation. Kanei-Ishii et al. [19] report that F-box and WD repeat domain containing 7, E3 ubiquitin protein ligase (FBXW7) of an SCF complex, targets c-MYB for degradation in a WNT1- and NLK- dependent manner. They show that FBXW7 directly binds to c-MYB via its C-terminal WD40 domain and induces the ubiquitination of the same in the presence of NLK in vivo and in vitro. The c-MYB phosphorylation site mutant failed to interact with FBXW7, suggesting that the c-MYB/FBXW7 interaction is enhanced by NLK phosphorylation of c-MYB. NLK bound to CUL1, a component of the SCF complex, while HIPK2 interacted with both FBXW7 and CUL1, suggesting that both kinases enhance the c-MYB/SCF interaction. In contrast to c-MYB, the v-myb gene product (v-MYB) encoded by the avian myeloblastosis virus was resistant to NLK/FBXW7-induced degradation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the FBXW family along with NLK, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4, NLK-FBXW4-SLC9A3R1, FBXW11-FGF4-NLK, FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK, FBXW2-JUN-NLK, NLK-FBXW4-WNT3A, NLK-SFRP1-FBXW4, FZD1-NLK-FBXW4, LRP5-NLK-FBXW4, FBXW2-FGF4-NLK, FRAT1-NLK-FBXW4, CTNNBIP1-NLK-FBXW4 and DIXDC1-NLK-FBXW4. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of FOX-NLK-X combinations

The FOXO family of forkhead box (FOX) transcription factors has a variety of important functions in stress response, metabolism, cell cycle, apoptosis, longevity, etc. The transcriptional activity and subcellular localization of FOXO are tightly regulated by post-translational modifications, including phosphorylation by various kinases. Kim et al. [20] report that the TAK1-NLK pathway negatively regulates FOXO1. They show that NLK binds and phosphorylates FOXO1 at Pro-directed Ser/Thr residues in the transactivation domain and the phosphorylation by TAK1-NLK pathway inhibits the transcriptional activity of FOXO1 and excludes FOXO1 from the nucleus, which is independent of phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase/Akt pathway. Consistently, knock-down of TAK1-NLK pathway dephosphorylates FOXO1 and decreases phospho-Ser-329 FOXO1 level. It also induces translocation of FOXO1 into the nucleus and leads to an increase in mRNA levels of FOXO target genes and poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase

cleavage. In addition, they show the interaction between NLK and FOXO1 is evolutionarily conserved in *Drosophila*. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the FOX family along with NLK, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FBXW11-FOXN1-NLK, AXIN1-FOXN1-NLK and DVL1-FOXN1-NLK. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FZD-NLK-X combinations

The WNT pathway activation occurs when a WNT ligand binds to a Frizzled (FZD) receptor at the cell membrane. Two different WNT signaling cascades have been identified, • non-canonical and • canonical pathways, the latter involving the β -catenin protein. Deregulation of the WNT pathway is an early event in hepatocarcinogenesis and has been associated with an aggressive hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) phenotype, since it is implicated both in cell survival, proliferation, migration and invasion. In a review by Pez et al. [21], record that the non-canonical signaling does not depend on β -catenin and requires ROR2/RYK coreceptors instead of LRP-5/6. In the WNT/calcium(Ca^{2+}) pathway, the complex formation between FZD, DVL/DSH and G proteins results in phospho lipase C (PLC) activation which cleaves Phosphatidyl Inositol 4,5 biphosphate (PIP2) into DiAcylGlycerol (DAG) and Inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate (IP3). This process results in the activation of protein kinase C (PKC) through DAG while IP3 promotes calcium release from the endoplasmic reticulum. Increased intracellular concentration of calcium enhances phosphorylation and activation of PKCs. This also triggers the activation of Ca^{2+} -calmodulin-dependent calcineurin and Ca^{2+} -calmodulin dependent kinase II (CAMKII), leading to Nuclear Factor of Activated T-cell (NFAT) and NLK translocation, respectively.

The WNT/ Ca^{2+} pathway activated by WNT5A antagonizes the WNT/ β -catenin pathway via an unknown mechanism. The MAPK pathway composed of TAK1 and NLK also negatively regulates the canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway. Ishitani et al. [22] show that activation of CAMKII induces stimulation of the TAK1-NLK pathway. They show that overexpression of WNT5A in HEK293 cells activates NLK through TAK1. Furthermore, by using a chimeric receptor (β 2AR-Rfz-2) containing the ligand-binding and transmembrane segments from the β 2-adrenergic receptor (β 2AR) and the cytoplasmic domains from rat Frizzled-2 (Rfz-2), stimulation with the β -adrenergic agonist isoproterenol activates activities of endogenous CaMKII, TAK1, and NLK and inhibits β -catenin-induced transcriptional activation. These results suggest that the TAK1-NLK MAPK cascade is activated by the noncanonical WNT5A/ Ca^{2+} pathway and antagonizes canonical WNT/ β -catenin signaling.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the FZD family along with NLK, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FZD1-NLK-SEN2, FZD1-NLK-SFRP1, FZD1-NLK-TLE1, FZD1-NLK-WNT5A, FZD5-NLK-SEN2, FZD5-NLK-WNT4, AXIN1-FZD2-NLK, FZD1-NLK-TCF7L1, FZD1-NLK-FBXW4, FZD1-NLK-WNT2B, FZD7-NLK-WNT3A, FZD8-NLK-WNT2B, FZD8-NLK-SFRP1, FZD5-FGF4-NLK, FSHB-FZD2-NLK, FZD1-NLK-PPP2R1A and FZD1-NLK-SFRP4. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of NLK in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the NLK, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For NLK, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

References

- [1] T. S. Gujral, G. MacBeath, A system-wide investigation of the dynamics of wnt signaling reveals novel phases of transcriptional regulation, PloS one 5 (2010) e10024.

- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [4] K.-W. Choi, S. Benzer, Rotation of photoreceptor clusters in the developing drosophila eye requires the nemo gene, *Cell* 78 (1994) 125–136.
- [5] B. K. Brott, B. A. Pinsky, R. L. Erikson, Nlk is a murine protein kinase related to erk/map kinases and localized in the nucleus, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 95 (1998) 963–968.
- [6] P. Coulombe, S. Meloche, Atypical mitogen-activated protein kinases: structure, regulation and functions, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Molecular Cell Research* 1773 (2007) 1376–1387.
- [7] T. Ishitani, J. Ninomiya-Tsuji, S.-i. Nagai, M. Nishita, M. Meneghini, N. Barker, M. Waterman, B. Bowerman, H. Clevers, H. Shibuya, et al., The tak1–nlk–mapk-related pathway antagonizes signalling between β -catenin and transcription factor tcf, *Nature* 399 (1999) 798–802.
- [8] M. D. Meneghini, T. Ishitani, J. C. Carter, N. Hisamoto, J. Ninomiya-Tsuji, C. J. Thorpe, D. R. Hamill, K. Matsumoto, B. Bowerman, Map kinase and wnt pathways converge to downregulate an hmg-domain repressor in caenorhabditis elegans, *Nature* 399 (1999) 793–797.
- [9] M. Yamada, B. Ohkawara, N. Ichimura, J. Hyodo-Miura, S. Urushiyama, K. Shirakabe, H. Shibuya, Negative regulation of wnt signalling by hmg211, a novel nlk-binding protein, *Genes to Cells* 8 (2003) 677–684.
- [10] M. Yamada, J. Ohnishi, B. Ohkawara, S. Iemura, K. Satoh, J. Hyodo-Miura, K. Kawachi, T. Natsume, H. Shibuya, Narf, an nemo-like kinase (nlk)-associated ring finger protein regulates the ubiquitylation and degradation of t cell factor/lymphoid enhancer factor (tcf/lef), *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 281 (2006) 20749–20760.
- [11] C. Kanei-Ishii, J. Ninomiya-Tsuji, J. Tanikawa, T. Nomura, T. Ishitani, S. Kishida, K. Kokura, T. Kurahashi, E. Ichikawa-Iwata, Y. Kim, et al., Wnt-1 signal induces phosphorylation and degradation of c-myc protein via tak1, hipk2, and nlk, *Genes & development* 18 (2004) 816–829.
- [12] T. Ishitani, J. Ninomiya-Tsuji, K. Matsumoto, Regulation of lymphoid enhancer factor 1/t-cell factor by mitogen-activated protein kinase-related nemo-like kinase-dependent phosphorylation in wnt/ β -catenin signaling, *Molecular and cellular biology* 23 (2003) 1379–1389.
- [13] T. Ishitani, S. Ishitani, Nemo-like kinase, a multifaceted cell signaling regulator, *Cellular signalling* 25 (2013) 190–197.
- [14] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [15] S. Da Veiga, Global sensitivity analysis with dependence measures, *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation* 85 (2015) 1283–1305.
- [16] A. Saltelli, Making best use of model evaluations to compute sensitivity indices, *Computer physics communications* 145 (2002) 280–297.
- [17] J. Martinez, Analyse de sensibilité globale par décomposition de la variance, *Presentation in Journée des GdR Ondes & Mascot* 13 (2011) 207.
- [18] M. Baudin, K. Boumhaout, T. Delage, B. Iooss, J.-M. Martinez, Numerical stability of sobol’indices estimation formula, in: *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Sensitivity Analysis of Model Output (SAMO 2016)*, volume 30, 2016, pp. 50–51.
- [19] C. Kanei-Ishii, T. Nomura, T. Takagi, N. Watanabe, K. I. Nakayama, S. Ishii, Fbxw7 acts as an e3 ubiquitin ligase that targets c-myc for nemo-like kinase (nlk)-induced degradation, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 283 (2008) 30540–30548.
- [20] S. Kim, Y. Kim, J. Lee, J. Chung, Regulation of foxo1 by tak1-nemo-like kinase pathway, *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 285 (2010) 8122–8129.

- [21] F. Pez, A. Lopez, M. Kim, J. R. Wands, C. C. de Fromentel, P. Merle, Wnt signaling and hepatocarcinogenesis: molecular targets for the development of innovative anticancer drugs, *Journal of hepatology* 59 (2013) 1107–1117.
- [22] T. Ishitani, S. Kishida, J. Hyodo-Miura, N. Ueno, J. Yasuda, M. Waterman, H. Shibuya, R. T. Moon, J. Ninomiya-Tsuji, K. Matsumoto, The tak1-nlk mitogen-activated protein kinase cascade functions in the wnt-5a/ca2+ pathway to antagonize wnt/ β -catenin signaling, *Molecular and cellular biology* 23 (2003) 131–139.